

EFFECT OF EIGHT WEEKS SAND TRAINING ON MOTOR FITNESS COMPONENTS AND PERFORMANCE IN LONG JUMP FOR BOYS AGED 14 TO 16 YEARS

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Abstract:

Sand Training involves various fine exercises which help in the development of Speed, Explosive Strength and Performance in long jump. Fifty School Boys were randomly assigned to experimental (n=25) and control (n=25) groups for the promotion of motor fitness components and performance in Long Jump. The experimental subjects, along with daily school schedule, underwent a Sand Training program five days in a week for eight weeks whereas control group participated in their regular school schedule only. As Sand Running Training were used to assess the levels of Speed, Explosive Strength and Performance in long jump. Data were analyzed by using One Way ANCOVA test. The results revealed that effect of Sand Running Training program helped to improve Speed, Power and Performance in Long Jump. The findings conclude that effect of Sand Running Training program helped to improve Speed Explosive strength and Performance in Long Jump.

Key Words: Speed, Explosive Strength, Performance & Sand Running

Introduction:

Long jump is one of the oldest track and field events, having its root in ancient Greek Pentathlon contest. From the evolution running jumping and walking have been a natural part of man's existence. And used them in search of food He also began to run for pleasure and then gradually for competition, leading to desire improve his speed or the ability to run further. There is great scope and need for research in Physical Education with applying the Training of Sand Running for development of Speed, Explosive strength and Performance in Long Jump on boys of age 14 to 16 years. The present investigation is aimed at collecting scientific evidence about utility of Sand Running in the promotion of Speed, Explosive strength and Performance in long jump. It is the outgrowth of the author's perceived interest in athletics. It is hoped that the result of present investigation may be helpful to those who are interested in the applied aspect of Speed, Explosive strength and Performance in long jump run through sand training.

Selection of Sample:

The samples were selected from the population of the Bal Bharti Public School, Delhi. Among 250 students the sample of 50 boys students from age group 14 to 16 were selected by random method.

Research Design:

All subjects of sample were divided into two groups. Each group consists of 25 students. The two groups were names as Sand Training group and Non Sand Training group respectively. The mean age, height and weight of sample were 14.26years, 134cms and 38.32 kg respectively .They were clinically normal and healthy.

Selected Variables:

Speed, Explosive strength and Performance.

Criterion Measures:

The following criterion measures were included to record the reading of various test items of motor fitness.

Variables	Test	Unit
Speed	50 Yard Dash	Time in Seconds
Explosive strength	Vertical Jump	Height in Centimeters
Performance	Long Jump	Distance in Meters

Treatment:

The training was administered to the Sand Training group only on sand for a period of eight weeks from Sunday to Thursday in the evenings. During the experimental period the subject did not involve themselves in any other activities vigorous in nature other than that training which was being imparted to them. The researcher gave the subjects an idea of Sand Running, its importance and the method of performing it. The training program was divided as **Warm up and stretching** (15 minutes) Slow Jogging, Striding, Normal Exercise, Stretching Exercise. **Sand Running** (30 minutes) 1 set 3 × 30 M Sand Run. 2 Minutes rest for second run. Some ABC exercises (stepping, Cskip, Sideward running, back kicking, lunging) **Warming down and loosing** (15 minutes) Slow Jogging, Stretching Exercise.

Statistics:

The data has been processed with general descriptive statistics and further they were analyzed using one way ANCOVA.

Results and Discussion:

Group wise comparison of effect of Sand Running Training for the Promotion of Speed, explosive strength and Performance in Long Jump for Boys Aged 14 To 16 Years. The mean achievement in **Speed, Explosive strength and Performance in Long Jump** due to Integrated Exercises Training Module, as obtained from One Way ANCOVA test, revealed that

- ✓ There was significant difference between mean score of Speed of school boys of the Sand Training group and Non Sand Training Group by taking Pre Speed as Covariate ($F_{y,x}=38.47, df=1/49, p<0.01$). Therefore the adjusted mean scores of Speed of boys of Sand Training Group is 6.98 which is significantly higher than that of Non Sand Training Group where adjusted mean Scores of Speed of boys is 7.35. Thus, the overall performance scores of both the Sand Training group and Non Sand Training group of Speed were not equal.
- ✓ There was significant difference between mean score of Explosive strength of school boys of the Sand Training group and Non Sand Training Group by taking Pre Explosive strength as Covariate ($F_{y,x}=276.58, df=1/49, p<0.01$). Therefore the adjusted mean scores of Power of boys of Sand Training Group is 16.53 which is significantly higher than that of Non Sand Training Group where adjusted mean Scores of Explosive strength of boys is 14.61. Thus, the overall performance scores of both the Sand Training group and Non Sand Training group of Speed were not equal.
- ✓ There was significant difference between mean score of Performance of school boys of the Sand Training group and Non Sand Training Group by taking Pre Performance as Covariate ($F_{y,x}=40.59, df=1/49, p<0.01$). Therefore the adjusted mean scores of Performance of boys of Sand Training Group is 14.25 which is significantly higher than that of Non Sand Training Group where adjusted mean Scores of Performance of boys is 16.20 Thus, the overall performance scores of

both the Sand Training group and Non Sand Training group of Performance were not equal.

These results help to interpret that the effect of Sand Running Program were useful in promotion of Speed, Explosive strength and Performance in Long Jump.

Conclusion:

Effect of eight weeks Sand Running Training Program intervention has potential benefits to improve Speed, Explosive strength and Performance in Long Jump.

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